

THE CONTENT OF IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT PROCESS OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERNIZATION OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In the world, attention is being paid to the implementation of coherence and systematicity in the management process of general secondary schools, the effective use of modern technologies of resource management in an innovative educational environment. In particular, in the conditions of innovative education, the development of modernizing mechanisms of management, the introduction of intensive evaluation instruments and strategies for quality and efficiency monitoring in the general secondary education system are gaining urgent importance. This article talks about the content of improving the management process of general secondary schools in the context of modernization of education.*

Keywords: *modernization of education, innovation, management, strategy, general secondary education, forms of management, management technologies, information, communication, education.*

Announcement

Management of educational institutions is a special field of modern science, which requires the leader to have specific work experience, as well as his unique organizational skills, talent, and personal qualities. The current development of the society shows the need to improve the professional skills of the heads of educational institutions. After all, the professional skills of leaders are a decisive factor in the organization of innovative activities in educational institutions in accordance with social requirements. Management is characteristic of any society, all spheres of life, and the main goal is to develop and improve production and all social relations in order to more fully satisfy the material and spiritual needs of citizens. Socio-political management is the management of relations between different groups of people (classes, social groups, nations, peoples, etc.) and relations between people within these groups. [1,65] In the existing sources, it is proposed to theoretically divide the practical activities aimed at managing the education and upbringing of the young generation, that is, pedagogical management, into the following three groups:

- 1) managing the process of personality formation organized by certain educational institutions;
- 2) managing the process of personality formation in the educational process organized independently in each institution;
- 3) managing the orientation of each component of education and training processes in the process of holistic development of a person.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Pedagogical management shows its own characteristics. For example: management in education has a moral dimension, which is defined by the word "acceptability". Educational management is both an art and a science, because in it relations with

people (in our opinion, it is appropriate to say subjects) and knowledge of the science play a large role; the dialectical unity of personal, state and public interests is reflected in the content of management. Public participation in education management is ensured. It is advisable to regularly improve the forms and methods that allow the use of various, including economic, social-psychological, organizational-pedagogical and other methods in the management of education. [2.45] In U.I. Inoyatov's opinion, it differs according to the level and directions of management of the educational system. Including: 1) according to level - internal management of state, inter-branch, network, local and general education schools; 2) according to directions - organizational, systematic, meaningful, from the point of view of personnel issues and methodical. [3.26]

According to R.Kh.Djuraev and S.T.Turgunov, school management is a collaborative activity of leaders and pedagogues. Science-based activities aimed at imparting deep knowledge and moral education, guidance on choosing a profession, and educating a comprehensively developed person.[4,78] In order to have an idea of theoretical approaches to improving the management process of general secondary schools in the conditions of modernization of education, to understand the essence of the concept of "innovative activity of educational institutions" and the content of innovative activity of educational institutions from a pedagogical point of view It is appropriate to express and define the principles.

Innovation is important in educational management. In the process of trying to understand the essence of the concept of "innovative activity", the following opinion expressed by V.I. Slobadchikov can be considered reasonable: "innovative activity is the incompatibility of traditional norms with new social requirements or the newly formed norm with the existing norm." It means practical activity aimed at solving complex problems arising as a result of the conflict between [5,4]

Based on the views on the stages of implementation of innovative ideas to the activity, it can be said that the activity of innovative management of general secondary schools is organized in the following four stages: 1. Identification of management problems.

2. Designing an effective management system.
3. Planning to create effective changes and innovations in management.
4. Implementation of planned effective changes and innovations.

The above-mentioned stages directly represent the content of actions aimed at preparation, planning and implementation, as in any activity. In order to achieve effective management of the activities of general secondary schools, the compatibility and applicability of the proposed innovative proposals will be determined according to the results of the analysis. When performing the analysis, the following three situations are taken into account:

1. Study and objective evaluation of the activities of general secondary schools before implementing innovative proposals (innovations).
2. Direct analytical study of the period of implementation of innovative proposals (innovations) in the activities of general secondary schools.
3. Analytical study of the situation after the direct implementation of innovative proposals (innovations) in the activities of general secondary schools.

Forms of innovative management of secondary schools: individual and collective; monitoring and control methods; and means - projects, schemes, maps, instructions, written reports, reports, etc. There are two different approaches to the management of educational institutions, the first is democratic (the participation of the pedagogical team, students and their

parents in management) and administrative (based on orders and coercion) management. In the conditions of modernization of education, working in accordance with democratic and humanitarian principles in improving the management process of general secondary schools helps to ensure the effectiveness of education. In democratic management, there is mutual trust and respect between the leaders and the team of general education schools, they work together towards a common goal while being able to understand each other, each member of the team (be it a leader or an employee), regardless of whether they are students) take a responsible approach to the performance of their duties and perform them seriously, conscientiously, and honestly.

In the context of administrative (bureaucratic) management, in our opinion, the implementation of conflicting rules and guidelines, mutual disagreements between subjects, lack of understanding and respect for each other, voluntary assignment of duties by employees, e.g. It is noticeable that they do it not with responsibility, but from a mandatory point of view, fear of pressure from the leaders. There is no mutual cooperation and solidarity between the administrative bodies operating on the basis of the institution (pedagogical council, parents' council, methodical association, etc.), they work separately, communication between them is weak, mutual information exchange is complicated. Each of the management bodies of the institution has separate goals.

In general, educational institutions based on administrative management, it is important to solve small problems everyday. Their way of working is based on deviating from traditional rules, and changes are not supported. General education schools also differ according to the direction of management, that is, managerial management and innovative management.

General education schools based on managerial management differ from the management procedure based on formalism and bureaucracy in terms of quality. Such educational institutions are characterized by relying on existing experiences, socialization of education, humanization and democratization. Their leaders intend to raise the activity of the institution to a certain level and maintain it, and prefer to use psychological-pedagogical and economic methods of management.

Research methodology. Changes in educational institutions, whose activities are led by a constant and productive innovative direction, are always supported. Mutual cooperation in educational institutions based on innovative management is a decisive catalyst of pedagogical activity. The organization of innovative activities in educational institutions is considered a process with a complex structural structure. Based on the study of available sources, the following parts can be distinguished in the structural structure of innovative activity:

1. Management - actions that serve to realize the goals of educational institutions and are organized in the process of management: analysis of the situation and opportunities; action planning (based on the program); organization of consistent innovative activities; leadership; control.

2. Level innovative activities - different levels of interdependence - reflect innovative activities organized within the framework of individual, group, general education schools, district (city) and region.

3. Subjects - persons who actively participate in the establishment of general education schools (institution director, management staff, subject teachers, class leaders, students, their parents, sponsors, etc.) reflects the essence of innovative activity organized by In this case, innovative activity is also evaluated from the point of view of the subjects' tasks.

4. Motives of innovative activity - represent the directions of activity, desires, professional abilities, habits, interests and aspirations of the subjects of general education schools.

5. The content of innovative activity is a unique management diagnosis, which describes situations such as identifying problems, innovative design, categorizing innovations, popularizing them, and analyzing results.

6. The process (cycle) of innovative activity - promotion of initiatives (innovative ideas), justification of innovative ideas (fighting with opponents), popularization of them, achieving wide adoption, time perspective of innovative ideas consists of a set of actions such as obsolescence, becoming commonplace, their rejection or content renewal (V.M. Demin, N. Fridman), distribution of updated innovations.

Analysis and results. The above-mentioned opinions confirm the conclusion that the innovative activity of general education schools is manifested as a system. A system is a set of elements forming a single whole, which are in constant relationship with each other and interrelated, and has the same essence as natural, biological, social. Characteristic features of a social system are clear goal orientation and organicity or naturalness. Integrality is a self-developing wholeness or unity, consisting of complex and layered stages. The naturalness and goal-orientation of social systems is ensured on the basis of the implementation of management tasks. Based on the analysis of the system, the following objects can be distinguished:

- input (everything that is necessary for the process and changes in it (subjects, equipment, information, etc.);
- output (the result or the final state of the system activity, the change of all things present at the input at the output);
- process (change of input to output);
- limitation (requirements for system process and results).

Competitive general education schools are entities that can meet existing social needs, provide a wide range of educational services, and update their activities in accordance with existing legal, informational, and psychological-pedagogical support. . Such general education schools are distinguished from other institutions by their high reputation, specialists with pedagogical education strive to organize professional activities in them, students are admitted to study on a competitive basis. Leaders can ensure stability in the provision of high-quality educational services, pay serious attention to strengthening the material and technical basis of the institution. In the process of improving the management process of general secondary schools in the conditions of modernization of education, the following tasks are solved: 1) decision-making; 2) announcement of decisions; 3) joint use of incentives and methods of improvement of activity; 4) correct distribution of tasks among subjects and leaders; 5) determining the consistency of goals and tasks of subjects and leaders.[6,22]

Conclusions and suggestions. Thus, in the conditions of modernization of education, improving the management process of general secondary schools is a leadership activity aimed at making certain changes in the practice of educational institutions, the effect of which is that the activities of general schools are in accordance with social requirements. organization, enrichment and improvement of the quality of educational content, increase in the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications of students, their possession of high spiritual and moral qualities, between teachers and students in the educational process determined by the decision of mutual cooperation.

In the conditions of modernization of education, leading principles have a special place in improving the management process of general secondary schools.

REFERENCES

1. Mirqosimov M. Theoretical and pedagogical foundations of school management. - T.: Teacher, 1995. - 158 p.
2. Ways to improve management efficiency in the system of secondary special vocational education in Uzbekistan. Authors: A.A. Khojaev, L. Hayki. Under the editorship of H.F. Masudov and G. Sonneveld. Responsible editor: Sh.Avezov. - T.: Secondary special vocational education center. 2001. - 147 p.
3. Djuraev R.H., Turgunov S.T. Educational management. - T.: "Voriz-Nashriyot" publishing house, 2006. - 263 p.
4. Slobadchikov V.I. Innovative education. J. School technology. - M.: 2005. #2. - S. 4-12.
5. Slastenin V.A. Podymova L.S. Pedagogy - innovative deatelnost. - M.: Izd-vo Magistr, 1997. - 221 p.
6. Inoyatov U.I. Theoretical and organizational-methodological basic management and control of education and professional college: Author. diss. dokt.ped.nauk. - T.: 2004. - 44 p.